

CERTIFICATION OF ENROLLMENT

Study title: "Italian Registry Chronic Pancreatitis (ITA RECIPE) "Registro Italiano Pancreatite Cronica"

Clinical trials number: NCT05733130

(here in after referred to as "Study")

Promoter/Sponsor: Associazione Italiana per lo Studio del Pancreas - AISP

(here in after referred to as "Promoter")

Principal Investigator: Prof. Gabriele Capurso

Coordinating Center: U.O. Endoscopia bilio-pancreatica ed Ecoendoscopia - IRCCS Ospedale San Raffaele, via Olgettina 60, 20132 Milano.

The Coordinator of the Study here declares that, based on the eCRF, the Centre IRCCS ISMETT have enrolled N° 7 patients in 2023.

Date: 18.03.2024

Name: Prof. Gabriele Capurso

Principal Investigator

Signature



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